

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office
650 Capitol Mall, Suite 8-300
Sacramento, California 95814

In reply refer to:
08FBDT00-2019-F-0043

NOV 27 2019

Acting Regulatory Division Chief
Attn: Naomi Schowalter
San Francisco District
U.S. Army Corps of Engineers
450 Golden Gate Avenue, 4th Floor
San Francisco, CA 94102

Subject: Formal Consultation for Pacific Gas and Electric Company's Ravenswood-Cooley Landing 115kV Reconductoring Project (Corps File Number: 2018-00466S)

Dear Acting Regulatory Chief:

This letter is in response to the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers' (Corps) November 5, 2018, request for the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service)'s concurrence that the proposed Federal action (Corps permit) for Pacific Gas and Electric Company's (PG&E) Ravenswood-Cooley Landing 115kV Reconductoring Project (proposed project) in the cities of Menlo Park and East Palo Alto, San Mateo County, California and any associated take of the endangered California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) and salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*) were considered in the internal section 7 consultation on the Service's section 10(a)(1)(B) permit for Pacific Gas and Electric's Bay Area Operations and Maintenance Habitat Conservation Plan (PG&E Bay Area O&M HCP). The Corps also requested concurrence with their determination that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the threatened western snowy plover (*Charadrius nivosus nivosus*) and its critical habitat (not a covered species in the PG&E Bay Area O&M HCP but considered in the internal section 7 consultation for the HCP). Regarding taxonomic assignment and nomenclature for the California clapper rail, until a time when the Service officially adopts changes made by the American Ornithologists' Union (from California clapper rail [*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*] to Ridgway's Rail [*Rallus obsoletus*]), the Service maintains the use of California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) as used in this current correspondence. Your request was received by the Service on November 7, 2018. This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR 402).

Updates to the regulations governing interagency consultation (50 CFR part 402) were effective on October 28, 2019 [84 FR 44976]. This consultation was pending at that time, and we are applying the updated regulations to the consultation. As the preamble to the final rule adopting

the regulations noted, “[t]his final rule does not lower or raise the bar on section 7 consultations, and it does not alter what is required or analyzed during a consultation. Instead, it improves clarity and consistency, streamlines consultations, and codifies existing practice.” We have reviewed the information and analyses relied upon to complete consultations in light of the updated regulations and conclude the consultation is fully consistent with the updated regulations.

The federal action on which we are consulting is the issuance of permits pursuant to section 404 of the Clean Water Act and section 10 of the Rivers and Harbors act to PG&E to conduct work in 0.632 acre of jurisdictional waters of the U.S. Pursuant to 50 CFR 402.12, you submitted a biological assessment for our review and requested concurrence with the findings presented therein. These findings conclude that the proposed project may affect, and is likely to adversely affect the California clapper rail and the salt marsh harvest mouse (both covered species in the PG&E Bay Area O&M HCP). You have also determined that the project may affect, but is not likely to adversely affect the western snowy plover which is not covered in the PG&E Bay Area O&M HCP.

In reviewing this project, the Service has relied upon: (1) the Corps’ November 5, 2018, letter requesting consultation; (2) the undated Biological Assessment for the Ravenswood-Cooley Landing 115kV Reconductoring Project (BA) prepared by H.T. Harvey & Associates; (3) the PG&E Bay Area O&M HCP; (4) numerous emails; (5) a conference call; and (6) other information available to the Service.

We concur with your determination that the proposed project may affect, but is not likely to adversely affect the western snowy plover or its critical habitat. Our reasoning for concurrence is as follows:

Western Snowy Plover and Critical Habitat

All project work is scheduled to occur between September 16 and January 30, outside of the nesting season. Biological monitors will conduct an environmental training informing construction crews about this species prior to beginning work, and in the event a listed species is observed within the construction zone, all work will cease until the Service is notified and further instructions are determined, or the animal leaves the area on its own. With the avoidance measures described by PG&E, we concur with the Corps’ determination the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect western snowy plover.

Towers 2 and 3 occur in designated critical habitat unit CA-14 for this species. Essential physical or biological features provided by the unit include sparsely vegetated areas above daily high-tides, such as salt pans, artificial salt ponds and adjoining levees, for nesting and foraging. Temporary impacts around Tower 2 would occur from installation of protective timber matting (or equivalent) for equipment access and tower foundation work; installation of reinforced foundations with equipment operating on the protective matting; and removal of the matting. These activities would be completed in approximately two weeks and no permanent impacts would occur. As such, we concur with the Corps’ determination the action is not likely to

adversely affect western snowy plover designated critical habitat unit CA-14.

PG&E Bay Area O&M HCP

You have stated that this project is a covered activity in the PG&E Bay Area O&M HCP. The following species may be affected by your action and are covered species under the HCP:

- California clapper rail
- Salt marsh harvest mouse

As described in the BA, this project is covered under the PG&E Bay Area O&M HCP as covered activity E9: Line Reconductoring, a description of which is on page 3-31 of the HCP. The Service issued an Incidental Take Permit (Permit Number TES6826C-0) (ITP) to PG&E, in October of 2017 pursuant to section 10(a)(1)(B) of the Act. The status of the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse and the effects of implementing PG&E's line reconductoring work were previously addressed in the September 28, 2017 intra-Service biological opinion (2017 BO) (Service file number 08ESMF00-2013-F- 0102) for issuance of the ITP. In the 2017 BO, we concluded that the effects of PG&E's operations and maintenance activities and level of incidental take were not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse.

Given that the proposed project is consistent with PG&E's HCP, we do not anticipate any adverse effects to the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse that were not previously evaluated in our 2017 BO. Thus, no incidental take beyond that anticipated in the 2017 biological opinion will occur as a result of the proposed project. We conclude that implementation of the proposed project will not result in jeopardy to the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse.

Therefore, the proposed project, if implemented as described in the O&M Plan, complies with all applicable conditions required by the PG&E Bay Area O&M HCP, ITP, and our intra-Service biological opinion and its associated incidental take statement. Therefore, by this consultation, incidental take for the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse for this PG&E project is exempted by the ITP for their Bay Area O&M HCP.

This concludes consultation on the Ravenswood-Cooley Landing 115kV Reconductoring Project. As provided in 50 CFR 402.16, reinitiating of formal consultation is required where discretionary Federal agency involvement or control over the action has been retained (or is authorized by law) and if: (1) the amount or extent of incidental take is exceeded; (2) new information reveals effects of the agency action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not considered in this opinion; (3) the agency action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in this biological opinion; or (4) a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the action. In instances where the amount or extent of incidental take is exceeded, any operations causing such take must immediately cease, pending reinitiation.

Please address any questions or concerns regarding this response to Kim Squires, Section 7 Division Chief, at Kim_Squires@fws.gov. Please refer to Service file number: 08FBDT00-2019-F-0043 in any future correspondence regarding this project.

Sincerely,

for Kaylee Allen
Field Supervisor